

Investigation of Medical Cu Isotope Production in Accelerators

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Abstract

Medical radioactive copper isotopes represent a significant advancement in the diagnosis and treatment of cancer, as well as in neurological studies and other medical applications. They facilitate the early detection of diseases, thereby enabling the implementation of more efficacious treatment modalities. The ⁶⁴Cu and ⁶⁷Cu isotopes are frequently employed in this context. The medical applications of ⁶⁴Cu are numerous, including cancer diagnosis, tumour tracking and monitoring of other biological events, examination of neurons and investigation of neurological diseases. It is also used for radiolabelling of biomolecules. ⁶⁷Cu is employed in targeted radionuclide therapy due to its suitability as an isotope for radiation therapy. This study will investigate the production of medical copper using low energy accelerators.

1. Introduction

Radioisotopes are indispensable in the field of medicine, facilitating precise diagnosis and efficacious treatment of a multitude of medical conditions. These isotopes are produced using advanced technologies, including nuclear reactors, particle accelerators, and radioisotope generators, each of which offers distinct advantages in terms of availability, efficiency, and the types of isotopes they can produce. Nuclear reactors, for instance, are capable of generating substantial quantities of isotopes and are particularly useful for producing isotopes with specific characteristics [1]. Particle accelerators, conversely, are particularly adept at producing isotopes with distinctive properties through the bombardment of target materials with high-energy particles [2]. Radioisotope generators are compact and portable systems that provide short-lived isotopes on-site, thus ensuring their availability for immediate medical use[3].

Radioisotopes play a multifaceted role in nuclear medicine, with critical applications in diagnostics, research, and therapy. In the field of diagnostic imaging, low-dose radioisotopes that emit short-lived beta+ and gamma rays are employed to create highly detailed images of internal organs and tissues. Techniques such as positron emission tomography (PET) and single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) rely on these isotopes to detect abnormalities at an early stage, including tumours, cardiovascular diseases, and neurological conditions [4, 6]. The short half-life of these isotopes ensures that the radiation exposure to patients is minimised, thus

making them a safe and effective choice for imaging procedures [1,3].

In a therapeutic context, radioisotopes that emit relatively long-lived but short-range, high-ionising radiation are employed to target diseased tissues with precision. These isotopes are particularly efficacious in the treatment of cancers, as they are capable of delivering high doses of radiation directly to tumour cells while sparing surrounding healthy tissue [8]. Examples of this include the use of radioisotopes in brachytherapy, whereby sealed sources of radiation are placed in close proximity to or within the tumour, and the utilisation of radiopharmaceuticals that have been designed to target specific biological pathways in cancer cells [3, 6].

In addition to their specific functions in either diagnostics or therapy, certain radioisotopes are sufficiently versatile to be employed for both purposes, a field of application known as theranostics [4]. The aforementioned isotopes facilitate a seamless transition from the diagnosis of a disease to its subsequent treatment, thereby offering a personalised approach to patient care [1,8].

The positron-emitting isotope ⁶⁰Cu, with its relatively short half-life and high positron emission rate, is particularly well suited to the rapid imaging of dynamic biological processes [2]. For instance, it can be employed in the assessment of tumour metabolism. The medium-length half-life of ⁶¹Cu enables the monitoring of biological processes over longer periods of time. It is suitable for positron emission tomography (PET) imaging and provides a balance between ⁶²Cu and ⁶⁴Cu in terms of the

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time required for administration [3, 6]. ^{62}Cu is suitable for generator-based use due to its short half-life. It is particularly suited to myocardial perfusion and brain imaging [4, 5]. ^{64}Cu is a versatile isotope that can be used for both imaging and therapy. Positron emission provides PET imaging, while beta and Auger electron emission are effective in cancer treatment [4, 7, 10]. ^{67}Cu is used in therapeutic applications due to its long half-life and high-energy beta emission. Gamma emission provides additional imaging [8, 9]. The most significant copper isotopes utilized in medical applications are summarized in Table 1, which delineates their fundamental properties.

In this study, the cross sections of the $^{64}\text{Ni}(p,n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ reaction (Figure 1), which is a pivotal parameter for the production of medical copper-64, have been calculated for different nuclear parameters and compared with the available experimental results.

Table 1. A summary of the fundamental properties of the most important copper isotopes used in medical applications.

Isotope (Half life)	Production Method and Decay Mode	Emission Types	Applications
^{60}Cu (23.7 min)	$^{60}\text{Ni}(p,n)^{60}\text{Cu}$ β^+ (93%) EC (7%)	Positron (β^+), Gamma	PET imaging, particularly for studying tumor metabolism and perfusion
^{61}Cu (3.33 h)	$^{61}\text{Ni}(p,n)^{61}\text{Cu}$ β^+ (61%) EC (39%)	Positron (β^+), Gamma	PET imaging; ideal for tracking biological processes over a longer duration
^{62}Cu (9.74 min)	Zn-62/ ^{62}Cu generator β^+ (97%) EC (3%)	Positron (β^+), Gamma	PET imaging, brain and myocardial perfusion imaging
^{64}Cu (12.7 h)	$^{64}\text{Ni}(p,n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ β^+ (17%) β^- (39%) EC (43%)	Positron (β^+), Beta (β^-), Auger electrons, Gamma	PET imaging, targeted radionuclide therapy, theranostic applications
^{67}Cu (61.8 h)	$^{67}\text{Zn}(n,p)^{67}\text{Cu}$ β^- (100%)	Beta (β^-), Auger electrons, Gamma	Cancer therapy, especially lymphoma and other malignancies; theranostic potential

Figure 1. ^{64}Cu production route by $^{64}\text{Ni}(p,n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ reaction in accelerators.

2. Materials and Methods

To analyze the production of medical copper-64, a thorough understanding of reaction cross-section values across a wide energy spectrum is crucial. Unfortunately, there is a significant lack of experimental studies that cover a broad energy range with minimal uncertainties. This gap necessitates theoretical calculations of reaction cross-sections for energy ranges not addressed by existing experimental data.

For this purpose, the latest version of the TALYS code will be utilized. TALYS is a powerful tool for modeling and analyzing nuclear reactions, widely used in nuclear physics and nuclear engineering [11]. Theoretical cross-section calculations in this study will incorporate parameters such as nuclear potential. The reaction cross-sections will be determined using various optical models, as outlined in Table 2.

Table 2. Outlines the microscopic and phenomenological optical potentials employed in cross-section calculations.

OMP No	Optical Model Potentials
0	standard JLM imaginary potential
1	0.44 replaced by $1.1e^{(-0.4E^{1/2})}$
2	0.44 replaced by $1.25e^{(-0.2E^{1/2})}$
3	as 2 but with $\lambda W(E)$ twice as large, recommended for energies below 1 MeV.
4	phenomenological optical model potential

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 illustrates the calculated cross sections according to varying optical model parameters and recent experimental cross section measurements. The TALYS code's default settings were employed for the remaining parameters, with the exception of the optical model. The calculations were conducted in 0.1 MeV increments within the energy range of 1 to 25 MeV.

Figure 2. Predictions of the developed model as a function of experimental values for coefficient of performance [5, 6, 7].

In all of the different optical model calculations, the cross section reaches its maximum value around 10 MeV (Figure 3). Below this maximum value, there is no consensus between calculations and experimental results, with the exception of a few energies. At energies greater than 10 MeV, there is greater concordance with the theoretical calculations, particularly with the work of Rebels et al. [7].

4. Conclusions

In this study, the cross sections of the $^{64}\text{Ni}(p,n)^{64}\text{Cu}$ reaction, which is a pivotal parameter for the production of medical copper-64, have been calculated for different optical model parameters and compared with the available experimental results.

No consensus could be reached regarding the theoretical calculations and experimental results at low energies. Consequently, the energy level density and gamma strength function models employed in the cross-section calculations should also be considered [12, 13].

Furthermore, the majority of experimental measurements in the literature were conducted using thick targets. Consequently, uncertainties in both the control energy and the cross section are relatively high in experimental measurements. More sensitive cross-section measurements are required for this reaction [14,15].

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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